

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING RESEARCH COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS BASED ON THE STEAM APPROACH

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Abstract

This article analyzes the role and importance of methodological approaches in developing the technological creativity competence of future engineers. In the modern education system, the priority of student-centered, innovative, and integrative approaches is substantiated, and the necessity of combining competency-based, activity-oriented, systemic, and individual approaches in the educational process is highlighted. Furthermore, the significance of pedagogical principles in developing technological creativity—such as the integration of theory and practice, problem-based learning, individualization, and continuity—is revealed. According to the research findings, the educational process organized on the basis of methodological approaches effectively contributes to the development of students’ professional competencies, creative thinking, and independent decision-making skills.

Keywords: technological creativity, competence, methodological approach, innovative education, integrative approach, activity-based learning, systemic approach, student-centered education, food engineering, pedagogical principles, creative thinking, professional competence

Main Part: Today, in the system of higher education, each student possesses unique abilities, opportunities, and life perspectives. Therefore, the educational process should прежде всего be organized with consideration of this individuality.

In the era of globalization and technological advancement, the development of technological creativity competence in future food engineers, as well as fostering their creative thinking and independent decision-making skills, has become one of the urgent tasks not only for educational institutions but also for society as a whole. In this context, traditional approaches are gradually being replaced by innovative and student-centered pedagogical technologies.

The process of training future engineers is no longer limited to simply transferring knowledge or developing certain skills. It now also includes important aspects such as personal development, creative approaches, and preparation for professional activity. Methodological approaches serve precisely this purpose—taking into account students’ individual needs and creating opportunities for them to fully demonstrate their abilities. In order to increase the effectiveness of modern teaching methods, it is necessary not only to apply interactive and innovative technologies but also to consider each student’s interests, aspirations, and needs.

Through methodological approaches, the educational process contributes to students’ personal development, professional growth, and their ability to find their place in society. This, in turn, paves the way for future engineers to become knowledgeable, responsible, and competitive specialists. In modern education, the principle of considering students’ creative thinking and technological perspectives is becoming increasingly relevant. The development of technological creativity competence based on methodological approaches should not be limited to traditional knowledge transfer but should aim to create a system that reveals each student’s individual characteristics, develops creative thinking, and helps them become effective professionals in their chosen field.

In the methodology of this research, the integration of various educational technologies plays an important role. First of all, organizing the educational process based on competency-based, problem-based, reflective, and individual approaches serves not only to provide knowledge but also to develop students’ independent

thinking and critical analysis skills. The results show that developing customized programs based on individual educational trajectories allows future engineers to enhance their technological creativity, and the use of methodological approaches in the educational process enables students to further improve their professional skills.

The concept of developing engineering education has become one of the key research directions in global pedagogy. Analysis of scientific literature shows that methodological approaches not only increase the effectiveness of the educational process but also play a significant role in the development of the field. It follows that an innovative approach involves organizing the educational process through the use of modern technologies, creative, and activity-oriented methods. Foreign scholars such as J. Schumpeter, D. Schön, and P. Senge interpret innovation as development through the implementation of new ideas in economic and pedagogical systems. Meanwhile, local scholars such as R.H. Jo'rayev, N. Muslimov, and A. Abdullayev consider innovative approaches as a means of improving the effectiveness of the pedagogical process through professional training, competency formation, and interdisciplinary integration. They also emphasize that innovative approaches are applied in conjunction with systemic, integrative, and activity-based pedagogical approaches in modern education.

The analysis of literature and our research indicate that the development of technological creativity competence in future engineers is closely related to the integration of scientifically grounded methodological approaches and pedagogical principles. This process is not random but should be organized as a holistic didactic system that connects clear goals, content, methods, and outcomes. In this regard, methodological approaches in training modern engineers serve not only to impart knowledge but also to develop technological thinking, creative problem-solving skills, and readiness for innovative activities.

Since production processes in industry are multi-stage, complex, and potentially hazardous, methodological approaches should encompass the following

requirements:

- a deep understanding of the physical, chemical, and biological foundations of technological processes;
- strict adherence to industrial safety and sanitary-hygienic standards;
- demonstration of a creative approach in designing and implementing new technologies and equipment;
- solving real production problems through innovative solutions.

Thus, methodological approaches represent a set of theoretical foundations that ensure the scientific organization of the educational process, defining its goals, content, forms, and outcomes in an integrated manner. They determine the principles, methods, and mechanisms through which pedagogical activities are carried out and play a decisive role in ensuring educational effectiveness. Their main task is to create an optimal environment for personal development, formation of professional competencies, and stimulation of creative activity.

In modern education, methodological approaches go beyond simple knowledge transfer and are aimed at shaping the learner as an active, independent, and responsible subject. They are characterized by general features such as those presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Approach Characteristics	Expected Outcomes
Goal-oriented	Learning outcomes are determined based on predefined professional and personal competencies;
Systematic	The content, methods, tools, and assessment mechanisms of education are considered as a unified system;
Scientific	Approaches are based on the scientific principles of pedagogy, psychology, and specialized disciplines;

Practice-oriented	Theoretical knowledge is closely integrated with real professional activities;
Result-oriented	The effectiveness of education is evaluated based on the level of formation of the targeted competencies;

In the modern educational process, methodological approaches are often applied in a complementary and integrated manner. This is because it is impossible to fully develop all professional and creative qualities of a future specialist using a single approach. Therefore, the integration of competency-based, activity-oriented, systemic, student-centered, and innovative approaches increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

In general, methodological approaches serve as the theoretical foundation of the educational process. Through them, pedagogical goals are clearly defined, the content of education is substantiated, and the ways to achieve the expected outcomes are scientifically grounded. This, in turn, is an important factor in ensuring the professional training, creative potential, and competitiveness of future specialists.

In developing the technological creativity competence of future engineers, the following methodological approaches are considered essential:

- competency-based approach;
- activity-oriented approach;
- systemic approach;
- integrative approach;
- innovative approach.

These methodological approaches can be applied step by step or simultaneously in an integrated manner, depending on the objectives of the lesson.

Considering the role of the main approaches in developing technological creativity, the competency-based approach directs the educational process from a set of knowledge to practical activity. Based on this approach, a future food

engineer acquires the competence to independently and creatively perform professional tasks such as:

- designing technological processes;
- optimizing production processes;
- assessing and managing technological risks.

In the modern education system, the scientific and theoretical foundations of these approaches show that preparing future engineers for creative activities, particularly in food production, involves the integrated development of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, creative experience, independent decision-making, and self-assessment abilities.

The essence of technological creative activity, its specific characteristics, pedagogical functions, and its role in the modern competency system are identified. Moreover, a system of effective pedagogical conditions necessary for preparing future engineers for such activities is substantiated. These include systematic organization, motivational approaches, self-assessment, differentiated instruction, a communicative environment, individual learning trajectories, and the use of adapted learning materials, all of which are important factors in shaping future engineers as professionals.

One of the key approaches used in training future engineers is the activity-oriented approach, which develops students' technological creativity through laboratory work, virtual modeling, industrial practice, and project-based activities. In this approach, the student is not a passive recipient of knowledge but an active problem-solving subject. Often, it is appropriate to integrate the activity-oriented approach with the systemic approach.

The systemic approach, which allows modern technologies to be considered as a unified system, emphasizes understanding the interconnections between raw materials, technological processes, equipment, final products, quality control, and

safety. This interconnected understanding is an essential condition for developing technological creativity.

Innovative and integrative approaches that ensure the integration of engineering, chemistry, biotechnology, automation, and environmental sciences, and encourage students to create new technological solutions, are widely used in international education. These approaches are also actively implemented in education under the framework of STEAM technologies.

According to Sharipov, the use of STEAM technologies should begin from an early age. Through this learning method, learners can understand the logic of modern phenomena and their interconnections. As a result, knowledge about the world is formed as a system, and qualities such as curiosity, engineering thinking, and teamwork skills are developed, which ultimately help learners reach a completely new level of development.

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